

Total Quality Management and Corporate Sustainability: A Literature Review

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Abstract

Literature review on TQM and corporate sustainability, many academics and practitioners examine the relationship between TQM and corporate sustainability. Many studies show that the implementation of TQM has a positive and significant impact on corporate sustainability performance. TQM helps companies improve operational efficiency, reduce waste, and increase customer satisfaction, all of which contribute to sustainability. Corporate sustainability based on the triple bottom line theory includes three main dimensions, namely economic sustainability reflects healthy financial performance, social sustainability reflects responsibility towards employees, communities, and stakeholders, and environmental sustainability reduces negative impacts on the environment. TQM can help companies achieve sustainability in all of these dimensions by focusing on continuous improvement, employee engagement, and social responsibility. Innovation capability can be a mediator of the relationship between TQM and corporate sustainability. TQM encourages innovation, which in turn can improve sustainability performance. The application of TQM for sustainability focuses on the process, this TQM emphasizes the importance of continuous process improvement. By improving process efficiency, companies can reduce negative environmental impacts and improve economic performance. Employee engagement is critical to the success of TQM implementation and corporate sustainability. Engaged employees are more likely to identify and implement innovative solutions to sustainability problems. Social responsibility in this case TQM encourages companies to be socially responsible. This includes paying attention to the environmental impact of the company's operations and contributing to the communities in which the company operates.

Keywords: Total Quality Management, Innovation Capability, Corporate Sustainability Performance

Introduction

Total Quality Management focuses on improving all areas of a company regardless of the type of industry. Practitioners and academics previously believed that TQM was only appropriate and suitable in manufacturing companies. TQM has become equally relevant in the service sector as well. TQM is a long-term strategy that aspires to achieve sustainable goals (Abbas, 2020). In order to successfully implement TQM practices or implementations, companies need to gain further insight into several related aspects, such as continuous improvement, top management commitment, strategic and tactical planning, and process control mechanisms,

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which will enable the company to implement the practices. By implementing TQM practices, companies advance existing processes and produce better quality product commodities (Jiménez et al., 2020). Although different companies have different organizational goals, customer value is essential in all areas and is critical for sustainable success (Sharma and Modgil, 2019). TQM has been established as a key driver in achieving competitive advantage and achieving optimal results (Abbas, 2020). Given the transformation in technology and operations, quality control techniques have been recognized and followed by companies globally, an example of which is the increasing number of companies adopting quality standards, such as ISO 9000 (Barua., 2021). Over the last three decades, there has been increasing interest in TQM as a strategy capable of providing competitive advantage to companies (Corredor and Goñi, 2011; Calvo-Mora et al., 2014). It can be understood as an organization-wide philosophy that requires all employees at every level of the organization to focus their efforts on continuous improvement of product and process quality (Corredor and Goñi, 2010).

The main elements of a TQM system can drive the generation of innovation in a company. The first is customer orientation. TQM implementation is customer-oriented, therefore placing customer needs and preferences at the center of management. Given that knowledge is the first step in the process of guiding a company's innovative efforts, it is logical to believe that TQM implementation will use the knowledge gained from customers to innovate its products and services. The second element that drives innovation is process management, with the main objective of reducing inefficiencies and increasing productivity and product quality. This aspect of TQM will lead the company to innovation in the process. Finally, one of the most important principles of TQM is continuous improvement (Sanchez and Blanco, 2014). This is one of the basic pillars of the TQM philosophy. The process of continuous improvement usually causes changes in the company, which translates into the development of new products, services and processes. In accordance with this principle, the implementation of TQM will encourage employee empowerment and participation in continuous improvement, which can support employee creativity. Flexibility is considered very important, as it is essential to adapt quickly to customers.

Quality is a highly relevant concept and a strategic key factor that plays a vital role in organizational success (Herzallah et al., 2014). Focusing on quality enables organizations to meet customer needs and wants appropriately, which ultimately, influences the realization of a better competitive position for business success (Lam et al., 2012; Fernandez-Perez and Gutierrez-Gutierrez, 2013; Aquilani et al., 2017). One of the most commonly adopted and prominent quality improvement philosophies in the contemporary business environment is TQM (Zu et al., 2010; Bajaj et al., 2018). Total Quality Management is a business management strategy that seeks to improve the quality of an organization's management, and therefore, increase its competitiveness and the value it provides to customers. TQM provides a competitive advantage for companies, because in the process it involves all divisions, departments, and various levels of the organization. A well-coordinated management process will result in lower production costs, as well as increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of production results, which will have an impact on improving overall business performance. As one of the main determinants of a company's success and survival, TQM is widely used by various types of organizations, from the manufacturing industry to the service industry.

The concept of TQM encompasses customer satisfaction (Muruganantham et al., 2018) by providing superior performance, continuous improvement centered on increasing productivity,

better product quality, reliability at lower costs, faster product delivery, and optimal utilization of organizational resources. In addition, the adoption of TQM principles leads to continuous improvement of the company's quality in operational processes, developing attitudes towards quality culture, customer and employee satisfaction to achieve long-term business sustainability while poor service quality decreases customer satisfaction and leads to organizational failure (Lagrosen and Lagrosen, 2019).

Total Quality Management is primarily realized as a continuous improvement of end-to-end processes to achieve customer satisfaction. This awareness is to adopt the quality improvement process by all stakeholders of the organization (Mahmood et al., 2014), thus resulting in competitive advantage (Li et al., 2018), along with customer and employee satisfaction (Syafiq et al., 2019). TQM includes four principles namely customer satisfaction, management by facts, people-centered management, and continuous improvement. Basically, it means adopting a continuous quality improvement process to meet the desires of internal and external stakeholders while encouraging teamwork, promoting people-centered practices, and integrating end-to-end processes with quality benchmarks and preventive actions.

Organizations that adopt TQM philosophy are able to generate substantial benefits such as high quality products, satisfied customers, reduced operational costs, improved performance in terms of financial measures, quality and innovation and even increased employee satisfaction (Zehir et al., 2012; Ahmad et al., 2013; Dubey and Gunasekaran, 2015). It provides a set of critical success factors that focus on continuous improvement, meeting customer needs and requirements, minimizing rework and waste, increasing employee empowerment and involvement, team-based problem solving, process management, supplier partnerships, top management commitment and support, human resource training and development, constant benchmarking and measurement of results using scientific methods (Agus and Hasan, 2011; Sabella et al., 2014; Aquilani et al., 2017).

Several studies have claimed the immense benefits of TQM implementation in terms of increased productivity, quality performance, cost minimization and elimination of waste which comprehensively leads to customer satisfaction (Baird et al., 2011; Brun, 2011). Other studies in this area have established that TQM activities help organizations reduce production process deviations and eliminate waste and scrap while improving quality performance (Modgil and Sharma, 2016). Several empirical evidences suggest a direct and indirect relationship between the adoption of TQM practices and the level of organizational performance (Nawanir et al., 2013; Tan, 2013; Sadikoglu and Olcay, 2014; O'Neill et al., 2016). Empirically, TQM as a strategy has proven its effectiveness in improving organizational performance in various aspects (customer satisfaction, finance, and productivity (Sadikoglu and Zehir, 2010).

TQM and Previous Research Review

A literature study conducted on the variables of TQM implementation and innovation capabilities on the variables of sustainability and company performance, the following is a summary of previous studies which are the main references in this study. Hudnurkar et al. (2022) found a structural relationship between TQM and corporate sustainability, namely analyzing the role of innovation capabilities. The design or methodology or approach used in this study is to conduct research in the context of the manufacturing industry in the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) sector in India. In the process, this study tries to put forward the importance of TQM and innovation capabilities in bringing sustainable practices

into organizations. This study uses Structural Equation Modeling with AMOS to study the relationship between TQM and corporate sustainability.

Hudnurkar et al. (2022) measured TQM through product control management, process control, vendor quality management and customer relationship improvement. This study found a direct relationship between TQM and corporate sustainability, along with its three dimensions, namely environmental sustainability, economic sustainability and social sustainability. TQM was found to be an antecedent of innovation capability. Innovation capability measured through product innovation, process innovation and managerial innovation did not mediate the relationship between TQM and corporate sustainability. However, the relationship between TQM and social and environmental sustainability was partially mediated through innovation capability at the dimension level. The practical implications of this study TQM can provide a holistic means to foster stakeholder participation and satisfaction to achieve corporate sustainability and in the process, can create an innovative culture to stimulate the circular social economy. The originality of this study fills the gap in the literature by providing a structural model that explains the relationship between TQM and corporate sustainability and suggests the role of innovation capability in achieving it. Jimenez et al. (2020) conducted a study to clarify the complex influence of TQM implementation on organizational innovation, in this case market orientation and knowledge management play a mediator role. The design or methodology or approach used in this study comes from a survey of 706 CEOs of Spanish companies. The results were analyzed using structural equation modeling to determine how TQM, market orientation and knowledge management affect innovation.

The findings of Jimenez et al. (2020) show that there is a non-linear influence between TQM and organizational innovation. Both market orientation and knowledge management perspectives play a mediating role between TQM and innovation. The practical implications of this study are that managers should be aware that TQM-based management helps organizations not only to achieve higher quality but also to be market-oriented and to better manage corporate knowledge; which will help companies develop innovation. The originality of this study raises the question of the relationship between TQM and organizational innovation that has received mixed conclusions in the literature. There is evidence in this study that the relationship between TQM and innovation responds to a non-linear relationship, in which a high level of TQM supports a more than proportional influence on the development of innovation. It also explains the mechanisms that produce this influence, with market orientation and knowledge management as mediator variables.

Sahoo (2019) analyzed that many organizations face competitive challenges due to the rapid pace of technological change. Both quality management and innovation are competitive factors that are deeply embedded in the organization's products, services, and processes. To achieve better company performance, manufacturing companies need to adopt TQM practices and develop innovation capabilities. Sahoo (2019) also tested the relationship between TQM, innovation capability and firm performance under mediation and moderation models using structural equation modeling. The design or methodology or approach of this study is quantitative. The data used to test the hypotheses were collected from small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in India who interviewed senior managers using a structured questionnaire. The hypothesized relationships were tested using data collected from 134 Indian manufacturing firms.

The overall findings of Sahoo (2019) clearly show that TQM through innovation capability is indirectly related to firm performance. This finding supports the idea that TQM practices drive product and process innovation strategies in manufacturing management, which positively impacts various aspects of firm performance. More importantly, this study supports the findings of previous studies that question the role of TQM practices in enhancing firm innovation capability. Some limitations of this study include: although a cross-sectional survey was conducted, the study did not allow for explaining the lag between implementation and performance. It also brought in the opinions of a number of senior managers of Indian manufacturing SMEs, and hence the sample size could be increased and the participation of respondents of responding firms could be expanded for future research.

Based on the results obtained, several recommendations are introduced to assist decision makers in manufacturing companies. This study contains suggestions for improving manufacturing company performance through developing innovation capabilities and adopting TQM practices. The value of this study extends theoretical contributions in production and operations management literature, suggesting how TQM practices and a company's innovation capabilities should interact in determining a successful organization and maintaining its global competitiveness. Tasleem et al. (2019) melakukan studi pengaruh manajemen teknologi terhadap keberlanjutan perusahaan peran mediasi dari TQM. Keberlanjutan perusahaan merupakan konsep manajemen strategis evolusioner yang kini telah mendapatkan banyak perhatian baik dalam literatur maupun praktik. Di era globalisasi dan digital saat ini, kekuatan persaingan manajemen teknologi dan praktik TQM telah diterima secara luas, namun sejauh mana strategi-strategi ini dapat berinteraksi dan berpengaruh terhadap keberlanjutan perusahaan masih belum diketahui.

Tasleem et al. (2019) described the important role of technology management and TQM in achieving corporate sustainability and to investigate the integrated relationship of the company as a research framework. The design or methodology or approach of this research is a survey-based empirical research conducted by developing a survey questionnaire and distributing it to multi-faceted business organizations in developing countries. Random sampling technique was used for data collection from companies listed in the Securities and Exchange Commission of Pakistan (SECP). Responses from 209 companies were useful for the analysis in this study. After confirming the questionnaire items for reliability and validity (content, criterion-related and construct validity) correlation, regression, factor analysis, path analysis and mediation analysis were conducted through SPSS and AMOS to assess the composition and causal relationship of the factors.

The findings of Tasleem et al. (2019) show that TQM not only has a significant effect on corporate sustainability, but also affects each dimension of corporate sustainability (economic, social and environmental sustainability performance), in this case technology management has an insignificant direct effect on corporate sustainability and only affects the economic sustainability dimension. Of the nine hypotheses, two hypotheses were rejected, indicating that technology management does not directly affect social and environmental sustainability. However, when the mediation analysis was run using TQM as a mediator, the effect of technology management on corporate sustainability was found to be significant, indicating that TQM significantly affects the relationship. Limitations/implications of the study are that the lack of response data can be a limitation for such empirical research. Given the practical limitations and risks in presenting mixed cultural dimension data, data were collected only from domestic organizations. Moreover, respondents in the local country were not very keen to

participate in such surveys due to the gap between industry and academia. The practical implication of this study is to try to examine the practices and levels of corporate sustainability, TQM and technology management among various industries, thereby, broadening a better understanding of the prevailing situation regarding these concepts in developing countries.

The research findings of Tasleem et al. (2019) although limited in conclusion, the findings can be generalized to other parts of the world if further research is conducted with more data. The social implication is that the results of this study draw the attention of the country's executive leaders and industry boards towards the implementation of the corporate sustainability agenda which is foremost in relation to quality and technology management practices. One of the major findings revealed that local organizations mainly focus more on the economic sustainability dimension, however the benefits of economic stability can be improvised to achieve environmental and social sustainability performance with the desired concentration on technological and cultural advancement and TQM practices. The originality or value of this study is unique in its scope and has been conducted in a developing country with a focus on the strategic concepts, and their interaction relationship, of corporate sustainability, TQM and technology management in the form of a proposed research framework or research model. This framework can be used or further studied for validation, by practitioners and managers who are working to lead sustainability management in their respective areas.

Firm Performance

Organizational performance is a key aspect in many studies in the management literature because it plays a vital role in developing, implementing, and monitoring strategic plans and setting the future direction of the organization (Teeratansirikool et al., 2013). Organizational growth and progress can only be achieved through continuous performance improvement (Gavrea et al., 2011; Mehralian et al., 2016). Organizational performance is an indicator that measures how well an organization achieves its goals. In today's competitive market, organizations must be able to evaluate their goals through performance measurement approaches, namely unit costs, profits, and subjective quality performance (eg quality, satisfaction), and determine appropriate strategies to achieve corporate goals. Many organizations have found that over-reliance on financial indicators to measure performance will produce short-term results (Johnson and Kaplan, 1987). Johnson and Kaplan (1987) argue that economic value includes the value of tangible assets and intangible assets.

Firm performance is one of the most prominent concepts in organizational research. Despite its importance, and despite the many developmental critiques that have emerged over the years, performance remains a difficult concept to apply in a scientifically rigorous manner. After eliciting three potentially viable approaches to conceptualizing performance, it was found that most studies were internally inconsistent in their use of these approaches, a situation that creates significant difficulties in interpreting the research effectively.

The main source of inconsistency lies in the use of a general abstract conceptualization of performance in theory building (a multidimensional approach) coupled with the adoption of one or two narrow aspects of performance in empirical research (a separate construct approach). Follow-up analysis designed to determine the best path to resolving this inconsistency suggests that the use of abstract performance in theorizing is not scientifically grounded and should be replaced by more specific aspects of performance to match existing

practice in empirical research. Although this change will have a profound impact on the field and will be resisted by many, it offers a real path away from untenable practice. There are several explanations for current practice but emphasize the forces associated with institutional theory. From an institutional perspective, it appears that firm performance is treated generically in many areas of academic life because it is embraced as an instrument of legitimacy rather than as a scientific tool that facilitates dialogue and the accumulation of knowledge.

Traditionally, company performance is measured and evaluated primarily by financial indicators, namely return on investment and gross profit ratio. In contrast, the balanced scorecard (BSC) introduced by Kaplan and Norton (1993) in Kaplan and Norton (2015) distinguishes between and integrates four different dimensions of performance indicators. BSC measures company performance through four perspectives, namely: customer perspective, internal processes, innovation, and finance. Mehralian et al. (2016) proposed a framework that integrates several dimensions in TQM with BSC.

Kaplan and Atkinson (1998) emphasize that, the cause and effect chain should encompass all four perspectives of the balanced scorecard. Internal operational excellence, such as short production cycle times and efficient internal processes, contribute directly to customer satisfaction and thereby improve financial performance as well. External customer satisfaction, measured by standards such as ordered product quality and on-time delivery, can be a major driver of a company's financial performance. Improving operational performance, through measures such as improving cycle performance and reducing costs, has been identified as one of the important objectives of TQM implementation.

Performance is generally an indication of the achievement of organizational goals. Organizational performance is defined as the output of a company's operations or the achievement of company goals. Venkatraman and Ramanujam (1986) divide business performance into three dimensions, namely operational, financial and organizational effectiveness. While operational or non-financial performance includes product quality, market share, market effectiveness and new product introduction; financial performance includes profitability and sales growth; and organizational effectiveness is the extent to which the organization achieves its effectiveness. According to Agarwal et al. (2003) and Guo (2002) organizational performance has two dimensions consisting of assessment/consideration performance and objective performance. Assessment performance includes employee and customer perceptions such as service quality, customer satisfaction, and retention. While objective performance includes financial and market-based assessments such as sales growth, profit, market share, and efficiency.

Corporate Sustainability

Corporate sustainability is the process of aligning organizational strategies to achieve socio-economic and environmental sustainability, using minimum resource utilization and waste reduction (Cai and Li, 2018; Davenport et al., 2019). Stakeholder pressure from customers, businesses and governments has led to the integration of sustainable development strategies (Ji and Zhang, 2019). Dyllick and Hockerts (2002) define corporate sustainability as the integration of ecological, economic and social aspects of the triple bottom line. Manufacturing industries, over the years, have caused irreparable damage to the water and air environment (Yuan and Xiang, 2018). Investing in the three dimensions of sustainability gives companies a competitive advantage in customer satisfaction, operational efficiency, and reputation from an

investor perspective (Calza et al., 2017; Singh et al., 2018). There are conflicting views on whether corporate sustainability is considered only from an environmental context (Marshall and Brown, 2003; Marshall and Toffel, 2005), an environmental and social context (Hall and Vredenburg, 2003), or a triple-bottom-line context (Bansal, 2005; Hart and Milstein, 2003). Montiel and Delgado-Ceballos (2014) cite an interesting critique in their study.

When asked what corporate sustainability means, half of them talk about environmental sustainability, although the other half mention people, planet, and profitability. Between 1995 and 2013, corporate sustainability was mainly discussed in the context of pure academic research. However, after 2013, the discussion evolved towards a practice orientation when empirical research began to provide solutions to business problems related to corporate sustainability. Jatinen (2022) suggests that positive customer perceptions of corporate sustainability lead to customer loyalty.

1 Environmental Sustainability

Environmental sustainability includes the protection of natural resources, reduction of air, land and water pollution (Kenneth et al., 2019), efficient use of energy, especially non-renewable energy (Ji and Zhang, 2019) and conservation of natural resources (Davenport et al., 2019).

2 Social Sustainability

Social sustainability implies a satisfactory responsibility towards the community and society (Asrar-ul-Haq et al., 2017). In other words, it means fulfilling the desires and well-being of customers, employees, government and other stakeholders. It encompasses initiatives aimed at the betterment of society without financial gain (Gorski, 2017); for example, developing inclusive public policies, health and safety measures and work practices (Ingenbleek and Dentoni, 2016) and spreading public awareness about the use of socio-environmental oriented products and services (Guerrero-Villegas et al., 2018).

3 Economic Sustainability

Economic sustainability (Matushevskaya and Katkova, 2017) is related to financial sustainability. It is based on the principles of efficiency, long-term prospects, flexibility, balance, consistency, efficiency and rationality, coordination, synergy, dynamic and hierarchy. Tasleem et al. (2019) found that TQM not only affects corporate sustainability as a construct but is positively related to each component, including social, environmental and economic. Technology management only has a significant positive relationship with economic sustainability and not with other dimensions. Zink (2007) visualized that the popularity and importance of TQM may be replaced by a stakeholder-based corporate sustainability model in the future.

Lai et al. (2015) found that strategic corporate social responsibility (CSR) addressed through organizational innovation capabilities can affect corporate sustainability. Tsou et al. (2021) argue that future research should focus on integrating TQM with CSR as its enablers and barriers. Green innovation capabilities, on the other hand, mediate the relationship between corporate economic and social sustainability and corporate performance.

The Role of TQM in Performance and Sustainability

TQM characteristics are characterized by its principles, practices or implementations, and techniques, and have been well accepted as a management model that provides competitive advantage to companies when successfully implemented (Antunes et al., 2017). The TQM

philosophy emphasizes continuous improvement and performance improvement to meet the challenges of ongoing competition in the market or business world. Reducing defective products will increase the yield of quality products and reduce the need for rework, errors and waste in staff, machine time and materials (Sadikoglu and Zehir, 2010). Continuously improving processes, product quality or services will reduce raw material scrap and rework, reduce waste and non-value-added activities and increase productivity, product design, product quality and lead time (Wu and Zhang, 2013; Antunes et al., 2017). Aligning product design with customer expectations and focusing on quality at all stages of product development and production processes is seen as a driver or trigger for product quality improvement and improvement (Sahoo, 2019).

This advantage will enable the company to gain greater profitability by increasing marginal profits (Kim et al., 2012). Successful continuous improvement efforts will improve the company's processes, products or services and enable it to meet changing consumer expectations or consumer tastes and customer satisfaction (Sadikoglu and Zehir, 2010; Antunes et al., 2017). A comprehensive literature review reveals that the majority of literature studies support a positive and significant relationship between TQM and company performance (Ebrahimi and Sadegi, 2013; Antunes et al., 2017; Konecny and Thun, 2011; Kim et al., 2012). TQM has been widely adopted by companies in the last 50 years, but companies report less than optimal results (Jayaram et al., 2010). However, three-quarters of TQM has failed completely or has created problems serious enough to threaten the survival of the organization (Valmohammadi and Roshanzamir, 2015). Therefore, there are some inconsistencies reported in scientific articles, which further call for empirical research studies on the relationship between TQM implementation and company performance to date are still needed. Based on the description above, this study predicts that TQM implementation has a positive effect on company performance.

TQM sustainability is a new construct that has emerged in recent years. Zink (2007) postulated based on stakeholder theory that corporate sustainability will replace TQM in the future. Earlier, Zairi (2007) suggested the transformational changes needed in TQM to have a competitive advantage in the sustainability domain. Tasleem et al. (2019) found that TQM has a significant effect on corporate sustainability and its components, while the impact of technology management on corporate sustainability is insignificant. Abbas (2020) found direct and indirect relationships between TQM and corporate sustainability, along with its components mediated through knowledge management.

Aquilani et al. (2017) put forward the critical success factors in TQM implementation, which together with the corporate sustainability ideology, will drive the creation of shared value in the organization. According to Rohit Sahoo, President and CEO, National Engineering Industries Limited (NEIL), CK Birla Group (Economic Times, 2016), TQM should be governed by continuous improvement, responsiveness, robust processes, employee engagement, and day-to-day work management. The day-to-day work management process should also be precise, simplified, standardized, and visually represented. Based on the description above, this study predicts that TQM implementation has a positive effect on corporate sustainability.

Conclusion

Sustainable competitive advantage of the company is important in maintaining the existence of the company in the competitive environment of similar companies. Companies can achieve sustainable competitive advantage by effectively managing unique resources to meet market needs. Competitiveness is a challenge for companies in product and service quality management to improve their performance due to the growth of similar businesses and the growth of digitalization. Therefore, it is important for companies to maximize competitiveness through a comprehensive quality improvement strategy by improving and evaluating company performance. The implementation of TQM contributes to sustainable benefits to achieve the company's goals in improving competitive position so as to increase market share and increase company profits. The best TQM practices that affect company performance, the dimensions of Total Quality Management that can be applied to influence the level of company performance are customer focus, continuous improvement, teamwork, and education and training. The study found that if the four variables are implemented, it will improve the company's performance position.

References

- Abbas, J. (2020). Impact of total quality management on corporate green performance through the mediating role of corporate social responsibility. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 242, 118-458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118458>
- Ahmad, M., Zakuan, N., Jusoh, A. & Takala, J. (2013). Review of relationship between TQM and business performance. *Applied Mechanics and Materials*.315,166-170. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMM.315.166>
- Agarwal, S., Krishna Erramilli, M., & Dev, C. S. (2003). Market orientation and performance in service firms: Role of innovation. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 17(1), 68-82.
- Agus, A. & Hassan, Z. (2011). Enhancing production performance and customer performance through Total Quality Management (TQM): Strategies for competitive advantage, *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. 24, 1650-1662. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.09.019>
- Antunes, M.G., Quirós, J.T. & Justino, M.d.R.F. (2017). The relationship between innovation and total quality management and the innovation effects on organizational performance, *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*.34(9),1474-1492. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJQRM-02-2016-0025>
- Aquilani, B., Silvestri, C., Ruggieri, A. & Gatti, C. (2017). A systematic literature review on total quality management critical success factors and the identification of new avenues of research, *The TQM Journal*.29(1), 184-213. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TQM-01-2016-0003>
- Asrar-ul-Haq, M., Kuchinke, K.P. & Iqbal, A. (2017). The relationship between corporate social responsibility, job satisfaction and organizational commitment: Case of Pakistani higher education. *Journal of Cleaner Production*.142, 2352-2363.
- Bajaj, S., Garg, R. & Sethi, M. (2018), Total quality management: A critical literature review using Pareto analysis, *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*.67(1),128-154. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-07-2016-0146>

- Baird, K., Hu, K.J. & Reeve, R. (2011). The relationships between organizational culture, total quality management practices and operational performance, *International Journal of Operations and Production Management*.31(7),789-814. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01443571111144850>
- Bansal, P. (2005). Evolving sustainably: A longitudinal study of corporate sustainable development, *Strategic Management Journal*, 26, 197-218.
- Barua, B. (2021). Impact of total quality management factors on knowledge creation in the organizations of Bangladesh, *The TQM Journal*. doi: 10.1108/TQM-06-2020-0145.
- Brun, A. (2011). Critical success factor of six sigma implementations in Italian companies, *International Journal of Production Economics*.131(1), 158-164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2010.05.008>
- Calvo-Mora, A., Ruiz-Moreno, C., Picón-Berjoyo, A. & Cauzo-Bottala, L. (2014). Mediation effect of TQM technical factors in excellence management systems. *Journal of Business Research*. 67(5), 769-774. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2013.11.042>
- Cai, W. & Li, G. (2018). The drivers of eco-innovation and its impact on performance: Evidence from China. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 176, 110-118.
- Calza, F., Parmentola, A. & Tutore, I. (2017). Types of green innovations: ways of implementation in a non-green industry. *Sustainability*, 9, 1301, doi: 10.3390/su9081301.
- Corredor, P. & Goñi, S. (2010). Quality awards and performance: Is there a relationship? *The TQM Journal*.22(5),529-538. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17542731011072865>
- Corredor, P. & Goñi, S. (2011), TQM and performance: Is the relationship so obvious?. *Journal of Business Research*. 64(8), 830-838. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2010.10.002>
- Davenport, M., Delpont, M., Blignaut, J.N., Hichert, T. & Van der Burgh, G. (2019). Combining theory and wisdom in pragmatic, scenario-based decision support for sustainable development. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 62 (4), 692-716.
- Dubey, R. & Gunasekaran, A. (2015). Exploring soft TQM dimensions and their impact on firm performance: Some exploratory empirical results, *International Journal of Production Research*.53(2), 371-382 <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2014.933909>.
- Dyllick, T. & Hockerts, K. (2002). Beyond the business case for corporate sustainability. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 11 (2), 130-141.
- Ebrahimi, M. & Sadegi, M. (2013). Quality management and performance: An annotated review. *International Journal of Production Research*, 24 (5), 5625-5643
- Fernandez-Perez, V. & Gutierrez-Gutierrez, L. (2013). External managerial networks, strategic flexibility and organizational learning: A comparative study among non-QM, ISO and TQM firms. *Total Quality Management and Business Excellence*.24(3-4),243-258. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2012.669558>
- Gavrea, C., Ilies, L., & Stegorean, R. (2011). Determinants of organizational performance: The case of Romania. *Management & Marketing*, 6(2).
- Gorski, H. (2017). Leadership and corporate social responsibility. *International conference Knowledge Based Organizations*. 23, 372-377.

- Guerrero-Villegas, J., Sierra-García, L. & Palacios-Florencio, B. (2018). The role of sustainable development and innovation on firm performance. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*. 25 (6), 1350-1362.
- Guo, C. (2002). Market orientation and business performance: A framework for service organizations. *European Journal of Marketing*, 36(9/10), 1154-1163.
- Hall, J. & Vredenburg, H. (2003). The challenge of innovating for sustainable development. *MIT. Sloan Management Review*. 45 (1), 61-68.
- Hart, S.L. & Milstein, M.B. (2003). Creating sustainable value. *Academy of Management Executive*. 17 (2), 56-67.
- Herzallah, Gutierrez-Gutierrez, A.H.L. & Rosas, J.F.M. (2014). Total quality management practices, competitive strategies and financial performance: The case of the Palestinian industrial SMEs, *Total Quality Management and Business Excellence*. 25(5-6), 635-649. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2013.824714>
- Ingenbleek, P.T.M. & Dentoni, D. (2016). Learning from stakeholder pressure and embeddedness: The roles of absorptive capacity in the corporate social responsibility of Dutch agribusinesses. *Sustainability*. 8, 1-18.
- Jaatinen, E. (2022). The effect of corporate sustainability on relationship marketing in tourism industry: the influence of customer perceptions of corporate sustainability on customer loyalty.
- Ji, Q. & Zhang, H.Y. (2019). How much does financial development contribute to renewable energy growth and upgrading of energy structure in China?. *Energy Policy*. 128, 114-124.
- Jimenez-Jimenez, D., Martinez-Costa, M. & Para-Gonzalez, L. (2020). Implications of TQM in firm's innovation capability, *International Journal of Quality and Reliability Management*. 279-304. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJQRM-09-2018-0233>
- Johnson, H. T., & Kaplan, R. S. (1987). The rise and fall of management accounting [2]. *Strategic Finance*, 68(7), 22.
- Kaplan, R. S., & Norton, D. P. (2007). *Balanced Scorecard* 137-148. Gabler.
- Kaplan, R. S., & Norton, D. P. (2015). *Balanced Scorecard Success: The Kaplan-Norton Collection (4 Books)*. Harvard Business Review Press.
- Kaplan, R. S. (1998). Anthony A. Atkinson. *Advanced Management Accounting (Third Edition)* Prentice Hall International.
- Kenneth, O.C., Nwadike, E.C., Kalu, A.U. & Unah, U.V. (2019). Plant growth promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR): A novel agent for sustainable food production. *American Journal of Agricultural and Biological Sciences*. 14, 35-54.
- Kim, D.-Y., Kumar, V. & Kumar, U. (2012). Relationship between quality management practices and innovation. *Journal of Operations Management*. 30(4), 295-315. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jom.2012.02.003>
- Konecny, P. & Thun, J.-H. (2011). Do it separately or simultaneously – an empirical analysis of a conjoint implementation of TQM and TPM on plant performance. *International Journal of Production Economics*. 133 (2), 496-507.

- Lam, S.-Y., Lee, V.-H., Ooi, K.-B. & Phusavat, K. (2012). A structural equation model of TQM, market orientation and service quality: Evidence from a developing nation, *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 22 (3), 281-309. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09604521211230996>
- Lagrosen, Y. & Lagrosen, S. (2019). Creating a culture for sustainability and quality—A lean-inspired way of working, *Total Quality Management and Business Excellence*. 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2019.1575199>
- Lai, W.H., Lin, C.C. & Wang, T.C. (2015). Exploring the interoperability of innovation capability and corporate sustainability. *Journal of Business Research*. 68 (4), 867-871.
- Li, D., Zhao, Y., Zhang, L., Chen, X. & Cao, C. (2018). Impact of quality management on green innovation, *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 170, 462-470. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.09.158>
- Mahmood, K., Qureshi, I.M.A. & Nisar, A. (2014). An empirical study on measurement of performance through TQM in Pakistani aviation manufacturing industry, *International Journal of Quality and Reliability Management*. 31(6), 365-380. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJQRM-03-2012-0041>
- Marshall, R.S. & Brown, D. (2003). The strategy of sustainability: A systems perspective on environmental initiatives. *California Management Review*. 46 (1), 101-126.
- Marshall, J. & Toffel, M. (2005). Framing the elusive concept of sustainability: a sustainability hierarchy. *Environmental Science and Technology*. 39, 673-682.
- Matushevskaya, O.A. & Katkova, N.V. (2017). Scientific and methodical approaches to forming the mechanism for ensuring the economic sustainability of industrial enterprises. *Оауковий в{сник Оац{онального г{рничого ун{верситету*. 5, 123-131.
- Mehralian, G., Nazari, J. A., Zarei, L., & Rasekh, H. R. (2016). The effects of corporate social responsibility on organizational performance in the Iranian pharmaceutical industry: The mediating role of TQM. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 135, 689-698.
- Muruganatham, G., Vinodh, S., Arun, C.S. & Ramesh, K. (2018). Application of interpretive structural modelling for analysing barriers to total quality management practices implementation in the automotive sector, *Total Quality Management and Business Excellence*. 29(5-6), 524-545. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2016.1213627>
- Modgil, S. & Sharma, S. (2016). Total productive maintenance, total quality management and operational performance: An empirical study of Indian pharmaceutical industry, *Journal of Quality in Maintenance Engineering*. 22(4), 353-377. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JQME-10-2015-0048>
- Montiel, I. & Delgado-Ceballos, J. (2014). Defining and measuring corporate sustainability: Are we there yet?. *Organization and Environment*, 27 (2), 113-139.
- Nawanir, G., Teong, L.K. & Othman, S.N. (2013). Impact of lean practices on operations performance and business performance: Some evidence from Indonesian manufacturing companies. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*. 24(7), 1019-1050 <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMTM-03-2012-0027>

- O'Neill, P., Sohal, A. & Teng, C.W. (2016). Quality management approaches and their impact on firms' financial performance – an Australian study, *International Journal of Production Economics*. 171, 381-393. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2015.07.015>
- Sabella, A., Kashou, R. & Omran, O. (2014). Quality management practices and their relationship to organizational performance, *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*. 34(12), 1487-1505. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOPM-04-2013-0210>
- Sadikoglu, E. & Olcay, H. (2014). The effects of total quality management practices on performance, *Advances in Decision Sciences*. 20(14) doi: 10.1155/2014/537605.
- Sadikoglu, E., & Zehir, C. (2010). Investigating the effects of innovation and employee performance on the relationship between total quality management practices and firm performance: An empirical study of Turkish firms. *International Journal of Production Economics*. 127, 13–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2010.02.013>
- Sahoo, S. (2019). Quality management, innovation capability and firm performance: Empirical insights from Indian manufacturing SMEs, *The TQM Journal*. 1003-1027. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TQM-04-2019-0092>
- Sanchez, L. & Blanco, B. (2014). Three decades of continuous improvement. *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*. 25(9-10), 986-1001. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2013.856547>
- Sharma, S. & Modgil, S. (2019). TQM, SCM and operational performance: An empirical study of Indian pharmaceutical industry. *Business Process Management Journal*. 26 (1), 331-370. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BPMJ-01-2018-0005>
- Shafiq, M., Lasrado, F. & Hafeez, K. (2019). The effect of TQM on organisational performance: Empirical evidence from the textile sector of a developing country using SEM. *Total Quality Management and Business Excellence*. 30(1-2), 31-52. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2017.1283211>
- Singh, V., Kumar, A. & Singh, T. (2018). Impact of TQM on organisational performance: The case of Indian manufacturing and service industry. *Operations Research Perspectives*. 5, 199-217.
- Tasleem, M., Khan, N., & Nisar, A. (2019). Impact of technology management on corporate sustainability performance: The mediating role of TQM. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*. 36(9), 1574-1599. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJQRM-01-2018-0017>
- Teeratansirikool L., Sununta S., Yuosre B. & Chotchai C., (2013). Competitive strategies and firm performance: The mediating role of performance measurement. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, Emerald Group Publishing Limited, 62(2), 168-184, January.
- Tsou, Y.H., Huang, Y.F., Liu, S.C. & Do, M.H. (2021). The effects of total quality management and corporate social responsibility on firm performance: A future research agenda. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*. 8 (4), 277-287.
- Valmohammadi, C. & Roshanzamir, S. (2015). The guidelines of improvement: Relations among organizational culture, TQM and performance. *Internal Journal of Production Economics*, 164, 167-178.

Venkatraman, N., & Ramanujam, V. (1986). Successful implementation of strategic planning systems: A path-analytic model.

Yuan, B. & Xiang, Q. (2018). Environmental regulation, industrial innovation and green development of Chinese manufacturing: Based on an extended CDM model. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 176, 895-908.

Zairi, M. & Alsughayir, A.A. (2011). The adoption of excellence models through cultural and social adaptations: An empirical study of critical success factors and a proposed model, *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*.22(6),641-654
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2011.580654>

Zehir, C., Ertosun, O.G., Zehir, S. & M Euceldilli, B. (2012). Total quality management practices effects on quality performance and innovative performance. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. 207, 273-280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.04.031>

Zink, K.J. (2007), “From total quality management to corporate sustainability based on a stakeholder management”, *Journal of Management History*, 13 (4), 394-401.

Zu, X., Robbins, T.L. & Fredendall, L.D. (2010). Mapping the critical links between organizational culture and TQM/Six Sigma practices, *International Journal of Production Economics*. 123(1), 86-106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2009.07.009>